

A Primer on Financing Trade in Islamic Law: Definitions, Sources, and Instruments

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I. Introduction

Muslims believe that Islam is the last religion. Islam is called the seal of religions. Islam, unlike the Talmud for Orthodox Judaism or Bible in Christianity, not only covers moral or spiritual teachings, but also it covers every aspect of life such as business. Islamic *shari'a* places religion as well as economics in the consciousness of Muslims. Therefore, Islam is comprehensive in coverage. Some rules in Islam may be stretched out to meet current issues while maintaining certain core principles as static. Indeed, Islam is a durable living force.

According to the teachings of the Prophet Muhammad (s.a.w), the pursuit of business is not inferior but honorable.¹ Allah's choice of prophet, who was a trader by profession from a trading society, highlights the importance of business.² The dominant tribe in Mecca, *Quraysh*, earned its livelihood for decades selling commodities for a profit.³

The holy Qur'an is filled with numerous verses using the language of trade. For instance, it states, "O ye who believe! Eat not up your property among yourselves in vanities; But let there be

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¹ S.A.W letters are abbreviations for the Arabic words "*Salla Allahu 'Alaihi Wa Sallam*". It is an Islamic term of respect typically following a reference to the name of the Prophet Muhammad. "Peace be Upon Him" is used by English speaking Muslims. However, "Peace be Upon Him" does not give full meaning to "*Salla Allahu 'Alaihi Wa Sallam*" words. Therefore, the words "*Salla Allahu 'Alaihi Wa Sallam*" should be used. See *Glossary of Islamic Religious, Banking & Financial Terms*, 6 J. Islamic L. & Culture 135, 148, 150 (2001). To determine if profit is profiteering, there must be an analysis of prevalent market prices and trading practices among similar merchants.

² See Chibli Mallat, *Commercial Law in the Middle East: between Classical Transactions and Modern Business*, 48 Am. J. Comp. L. 81, 92 (2000) (a long-standing tradition of Islamic civilization is its association with and the centrality of trade. The tradition relating to the other great monotheistic epigones in the figures of Abraham and Jesus does not acknowledge the centrality of trade and commerce in any similar way. In the case of Jesus, the episode of the Temple merchants even points in the opposite direction, with the mercantile pursuit of wealth depicted in a derogatory manner. Neither classical Christianity or Judaism seems to have extolled the virtues of commerce in such a detailed or enthusiastic argument for the commercial professions as did *Dimashqi* in his *Mahasin al-tijara*, The Virtues of Commerce).

³ See Gene W. Heck, *The Economic Dynamic of the Early Islamic State* 43-44 (1995).

amongst you traffic and trade by mutual good will”.⁴ This verse signifies trade on the basis of mutual consent free from undue interference. The Qur’an also states, “For the covenants (Of security and safeguard Enjoyed) by the Quraysh, Their covenants (covering) journeys by winter and summer- Let them adore the Lord of this House, Who provides them With food against hunger, And with security Against fear (of danger)”.⁵ Hence, Islamic finance has its roots in the camel caravans that used to travel along major trade routes. Merchants would provide money for traders to buy and transport goods, profiting from a successful caravan or losing if the caravan got lost during its journey.

There are limitations on trade or business in Islam such as prohibition of speculation and interest, i.e. the centerpiece of Islamic economics.⁶ Islamic *shari’a* purifies business transactions. The market for *shari’a* compliant financing transactions has grown significantly in the past years.⁷ Even, Western institutions have become increasingly involved in Islamic financing.⁸

Shari’a compliant retail products, from home and auto mortgages and checking accounts, to bond

⁴ See Qur’an 4:29. See also Qur’an 2:282, 17:66, 24:37, 35:28, and 62:11.

⁵ *Id.* 106:1-4. The historical background of these verses is that the *Quraysh*, the dominant tribe in Mecca, conducted international trade by setting out two caravan journeys, one from Mecca to the warmth of Syria in summer and the other to the cooler Yemen in winter, to sell cheaper leather and clothing than those made in Syria and Yemen. Thus, trade provided them with a living. However, for the safety of these caravans, trade agreements were concluded with the tribes on the routes. In return, the *Quraysh*, agreed to collect these tribes’ goods to sell, and on the way back hand them over other goods. See Patricia Crone, *Meccan Trade and the Rise of Islam* 109, 205-209 (Princeton U. Press 1987).

⁶ See Timur Kuran, *The Discontents of Islamic Economic Morality*, 86 *Am. Econ. Rev.* 438, 439 (1996) (Islamic economics is dedicated to restructuring economic thought and practice on the basis of fundamental Islamic teachings. Its founders were Indian Muslims in the 1940s. Sayyid Abu ‘l-A’la Maududi coined the term “Islamic economics” around the time of India’s partition. Afterward, Pakistanis have made the largest contribution to the literature. The blanket prohibition against interest became the centerpiece of Islamic economics. Attention then turned to issues such as rules of barter, rights of slaves, and transactions. The intended effect of Islamic economics is to reform human nature. The goal of Islamic economics is to transform selfish and acquisitive Homo economicus into a paragon of virtue, Homo Islamicus).

⁷ See Bjorn Sorenson, *Ethical Money: Financial Growth in the Muslim World*, 23 *Am. U. Int’l L. Rev.* 647, 657 (2008). See also Theodore Karasik, Frederic Wehrey & Steven Strom, *Islamic Finance in Global Context: Opportunities and Challenges*, 7 *Chi. J. Int’l L.* 379 (2007).

⁸ See Kimberly J. Tacy, *Islamic Finance: A Growing Industry in the United States*, 10 *N.C. Banking Inst.* 355, 366 (2006) (Until 1997, financial institutions in the U.S. did not offer formal Islamic financing that was both sanctioned by a Shari’ah Board and publicly approved by a U.S. regulatory agency. Today, nine entities now offer formal Islamic financing products in the U.S., with many customizing loan products for Muslim clients on an as-needed basis).

(*sukuk*) issuance and project finance requirements, as well as derivative transactions are just some of the product applications being designed for the Islamic financial markets.⁹

Thirty years ago, Islamic finance was barely known as a concept, and its applications were tightly used. Today, Islamic financial institutions are successfully operating in the Muslim world and western countries as well. More than 250 Islamic financial institutions are operating in over 50 countries world wide.¹⁰ Islamic finance has managed to attract the attention of global finance while becoming a major driver for the economies in Muslim-majority countries. The existing Islamic finance market stands at an estimated \$1.35 trillion in assets based on disclosed assets by all Islamic finance institutions and are growing at a phenomenal rate of 15-20 percent.¹¹ Leading countries such as the United Kingdom have become the first non-Islamic country to operate Islamic products of insurance and *sukuk*.¹² The sector of Islamic banking is inviting foreign investments, gaining popularity and steadily rising to become a flourishing industry by all means.

Many non-Islamic banks are involved in Islamic finance. For example, Deutsche Bank, HSBC, Standard Chartered and Barclay's have their investment banks serving as international lead arrangers of Islamic bonds (*sukuk*) issuances.¹³ Many conventional banks established

⁹ See Ayman H. Abdel-Khaleq and Christopher F. Richardson, *New Horizons for Islamic Securities: Emerging Trends in Sukuk Offerings*, 7 Chi. J. Int'l L. 409, 413-429 (2007) (discussing *sukuk* and the *sukuk* market) See also Scott Griswold, *A Redeeming Interest in Religious Freedom: Are Islamic Mortgage Alternatives Clogs on the Equitable Right of Redemption?* 13 Fordham J. Corp. & Fin. L. 419, 426 (2008).

¹⁰ Countries where Islamic financial institutions are already functioning well include Albania, Algeria, Australia, the Bahamas, Canada, France, Iran, Iraq, Italy, Cote D'Ivoire, Jordan, Kuwait, Morocco, the Netherlands, Niger, Palestine, Qatar, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, South-Africa, Switzerland, Tunisia, Turkey, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom, the U.S. to mention a few. See Ajagbe T. S and Brimah, A. N., *Islamic banking development and Evolution: current issues and future prospects*, 3.2 Journal of Research in International Business and Management 73-79 (2013).

¹¹ See Muzaffar Rizvi, *A Flourishing Industry*, Khaleej Times (Nov. 25, 2013).

¹² The United Kingdom has introduced a series of tax and legislative changes to help transform the United Kingdom into the global hub of Islamic finance. In 2007, the United Kingdom enacted the Finance Act which sought to facilitate *sukuk* issuance. important purpose of the Finance Act of 2007 was to treat *sukuks* as conventional bonds and apply the same applicable tax treatment. Moreover, the United Kingdom established the world's first secondary market for *sukuk* offerings that has led to a significant growth in *sukuk* offerings in the United Kingdom. See Lionel Laurent, *Contenders for the Crown*, Forbes, (Apr. 21, 2008) (discussing London's potential as Islamic finance hub and United States' ambivalence to Shari'ah-compliant products).

¹³ See Rizvi,, *supra* note 11.

Islamic windows to separate Islamic banking subsidiaries.¹⁴ An Islamic window within the conventional bank brings about a wide expansion of economies due to its built-in expertise of banking. Moreover, the bank already possesses the ability to provide various Islamic banking products which will enable them to grab large number of customers who prefer Islamic banking. This way the conventional banks can function and serve the conventional customers and the Islamic window operates in its activities with complete separation from its parent bank and serves its customers.¹⁵ However, presence of Islamic windows leads to the mixing of funds which will be further used by the Islamic windows to finance its customers. Therefore, despite the functional benefits of Islamic windows in conventional banks, the absence of the foundation of its creation i.e. *shari'a* compliance, may nullify the importance of its existence.

The article will provide analysis of Islamic finance, including its underpinnings. The article also discusses the fundamental Islamic legal mechanics as compared to conventional finance and then examines the main forms of Islamic finance. However, before discussing Islamic law and its relation to finance it would be helpful to provide a background of Islamic law, one of the world's major legal systems along with Jewish law (Halacha), civil law, and common law. The discussion of sources of Islamic law is essential to understanding Islamic finance since it is governed by this divine law, the *shari'a*.

¹⁴ The U.S. Federal Reserve authorized leading U.S. financial institutions to offer murabaha and ijara products in countries, such as Pakistan and the Sudan, that had mandated that all financing activities in those countries be provided on an Islamic basis. Few financial institutions in the U.S. use ijara, murabaha, and musharaka financing structures to provide Shari'ah-compliant mortgages. See Haider Ala Hamoudi, *The Impossible, Highly Desired Islamic Bank*, 5 WM. Mary Bus. L. Rev. 105, 179 (2014).

¹⁵ See Juan Solé, *Introducing Islamic Banks Into Conventional Banking System*, IMF Working Paper WP/07/175 (2007).

II. Sources of Law in Islam

The law or *shari'a* in Islam may be thought of as being composed of at least two parts: revealed and non-revealed.¹⁶ The revealed form of *shari'a* has two proper sources: the Qur'an (the holy book) and the *sunna* (traditions based on the *hadith*, sayings and actions of the prophet).¹⁷ Non-revealed sources of *shari'a*, developed by Muslim jurists after the revelation of the Qur'an and the *sunna*, include *ijma* (consensus of Muslim scholars on a point of law) and *qiyas* (a sub-*ijtihad* species of strict analogical reasoning). These are the authoritative sources of jurisprudence (*usul al-fiqh*).¹⁸ *Usul al-fiqh* incorporates both deductive (from broad general principles in the law to a particular case) and inductive (from a particular case to general principles) methods of reasoning.

Other sources of non-revealed *shari'a* include *ijtihad* (individual intellectual effort and wider independent reasoning), *istihsan* (equity or juristic preference), *istishab* (presumption of continuity), *istislah* or *maslaha* (opinion based on public interest), *darura* (necessity), *urf* (custom), and *fatwa* giving (*responsa*) of *muftis* (jurisconsults) such as the Egyptian grand *mufti* Muhammad 'Abduh.¹⁹

¹⁶ *Shari'a* is an Arabic word meaning way. The *shari'a* was compiled during the first three centuries after Muhammad's (s.a.w) death. See Ahmed Zaki Yamani, *The Eternal Shari'a*, 12 N.Y.U. J. Intl. L. & Pol. 205, 205-06 (1979).

¹⁷ The Qur'an is divided into 114 chapters, known as *surahs*. Each *surah* is divided into verses, called "ayas" which mean "signs", referring to signs from and of Allah. There are roughly 6000 verses. See Bhala, *infra* note 19, at 680.

¹⁸ See William M. Ballantyne & Howard L. Stovall, *Arab Commercial Law: Principles and Perspectives* 28-30 (ABA 2002). See also John Walbridge, *Logic in the Islamic Intellectual Tradition: The Recent Centuries*, Vol. 39 No. 1 *Islamic Stud.* 55, 68 (2000) (Islamic law is divided into two disciplines: *fiqh*, which the content of the sacred law, and *usul al-fiqh*, the principles by which it is deduced. *Usul* is a system of rules by which new law is derived from a fixed body of source materials. It deals with such problems as how to derive a general rule from a known particular case, how words can legitimately be interpreted, and so on).

¹⁹ See Hasbullah Haji Abdul Rahman, *The Origin and Development of Ijtihad to Solve Modern Complex Legal Problems*, Vol. 43 *The Islamic Q.* 73, 75-76 (No. 2, 1999) (*ijtihad* must not be exercised as to the existence of Allah, the trism of the prophets of Allah, and the authenticity of the Qur'an. To exercise *ijtihad* a Muslim has to be knowledgeable of the Qur'an, *sunna*, and *usul al-fiqh*. A Muslim also must be a good Muslim, pious and law-abiding, and not influenced by heresy, just, and reliable). See also *Islamic Legal Interpretation: Muftis and their Fatwas* 4-32, 286-296 (Muhammad Khalid Masud et al. eds., Harvard U. Press 1996) (a *fatwa* is a nonbinding advisory opinion to an individual questioner (*mustafti*) in connection with ongoing human affairs. A *fatwa* may cover issues concerning mosques, intergenerational transmission of property, and marriage of children, and banking

To establish direct support for a legal proposition a Muslim legal scholar should be able to pinpoint to a verse of the Qur'an, or at least a tradition or *hadith* of the Prophet Muhammad (s.a.w). While the Qur'an provides the written law, the *sunna* supplies a sort of case law, consistent with the Qur'anic text. The *sunna* embodies the application of the Qur'an's written law to concrete disputes and hypothetical questions that arose during the prophet's life. Some *sunna* cases simply explain the Qur'anic principles and rules. Some cases interpret the Qur'anic text by providing new insights into the written law. Some provide new principles and rules, supplementing the Qur'an's protected knowledge.

If direct support of a legal proposition in the Qur'an and *sunna* is not possible, then a Muslim legal scholar seeks an instance when all legal scholars or jurists agree on a particular point of law or interpretation. Consensus may be relied upon as a valid source of law. Use of analogical reasoning, *qiyas*, is quite strict. First, one must find a verse in the Qur'an, a *sunna* of the prophet, or a rule on which consensus was achieved as the point of departure. Then the direct cause, purpose or rationale, narrowly conceived, must be determined, and the relationship between the two concerns, the one in which there is a rule and the one to which one is considering extending the rule, must be elucidated in such a way as to demonstrate that the rule should be extended. For example, the Qur'anic prohibition of drinking wine extends to other alcoholic beverages without concern about gray areas. On the other hand, the relaxation of the duty to fast in cases of illness

operations and interest. *Fatwa* began as a private activity that was independent of any state control before being transformed into a mechanism of religious legitimization. The formulation of *fatwa* is patterned after a question-answer model. Important *muftis* in the pre-modern era were *Mu'adh b. Jabal*, *Ibn 'Abbas*, and *Ibn Rushd*. Modern era *muftis* include *Muhammad Sayyid Tantawi*, grand *mufti* of the Egyptian Republic and head of *Dar al-ifta'*, *Makhluf* (*Fatwa* Office), *al-Qaradawi*, and 'Abd al-'Aziz b. 'Abd Allah Ibn Baz.). An example of the use of *fatwa* as a mechanism of religious legitimization is the plan of Egypt's Ministry of Religious Affairs in 2004 to connect all 5,000 of Cairo's mosques to a city-wide wireless network, so that five times a day the Muslim call to prayer [*adhan*] could be broadcast in a single voice, in the same instant. To counter criticism for the idea as *bid'a* (irreligious innovation), the Ministry obtained several *fatwas*.

and traveling cannot be extended so easily.²⁰ Applying the concept of hardship to the deliberation is not helpful because travelers would not always find fasting a hardship. Moreover, *hardship* is a very broad and fuzzy concept. The divine purpose or cause of the rule is not mere hardship, and so extension of the relaxation would not be discrete or defined.

All Muslim scholars agree that the Qur'an is the core of Islamic law. However, there is disagreement among them about the rank of other sources of Islamic law. Consequently, there have arisen four main schools of law in *Sunni*: the Hanafi, Maliki, Shafi'i, and Hanbali.²¹ Hanafi scholars rely on reason and opinion, using analogy and equity as sources of law. The Maliki school requires strict application of the *sunna* of the Prophet and minimizes the role of opinion. The Shafi'i school has tried to reconcile the Maliki and Hanafi principles.²² The Hanbali school is well known for its strict adherence to the text of the Qur'an and the *sunna*. Analogy is recognized as a source of Hanbali law.

The *shari'a* tries to describe all possible human acts, classify it as obligatory, recommended, neutral, objectionable, or forbidden by Allah (s.w.t), the supreme legislator.²³ Islamic law addresses matters ranging from the timing of daily prayers and prohibitions against eating certain foods to marriage, inheritance, and commerce. The Qur'an speaks much more explicitly and

²⁰ See Gamal M. Badr, *Islamic Law: Its Reaction to Other Legal Systems*, 26 Am. J.Comp.L. 187, 189 (1978).

²¹ Islam embraces two principal branches: Sunnism, the majority faith, and Shi'ism. The most important group in Shi'ism is the Twelvers. Other Shi'ism schools include Ismailism and Zeydism. See Yann Richard, *Shi'ite Islam: polity, ideology, and creed* 1, 5-9 (Antonia Nevill trans., Blackwell 1995) (Shi'ites are Muslims, like the Sunnis, but there are differences between them. Unlike Sunnism which insists on the arbitrary will of Allah, Shi'ism proclaims that Allah can only act within the bounds of justice. The Imam in Shi'ism plays a fundamental role in the relations between Allah and man. Moreover, Shi'ite doctrines are based on collections of traditions quite distinct from those of the Sunnis. Shi'ite doctrine varies noticeably from Sunni as regards inheritance and marriage). See David Bonderman, *Modernization and Changing Perception of Islamic Law*, 81 Harv. L. Rev. 1169, 1174 (1968) (schools of law in *Sunni* appeared in the first and second centuries of Islam. They developed initially due to geographical separation-one at Medina, one at Kufa in Iraq, one in Syria- for example. After a few centuries, each school became personalized and took the name of its leading scholar. Each school developed its own body of legal doctrine, but they were similar in broad precepts. They disagreed as to particular points of law).

²² Al Shafi'i, the founder of al-Shafi'i law school, has been known as the founder of Islamic jurisprudence. He was the first jurist to compile and systematize Islamic sources of law.

²³ S.W.T letters are abbreviations of the words "*Subhanahu Wa Ta'ala*" which means that *Allah* is purified of having partners or sons. When the name of Almighty Allah is pronounced, a Muslim is to show his respect to him by reciting these words. See *Glossary of Islamic Religious, Banking & Financial Terms*, *supra* note 1, at 153.

completely about personal status (marriage and inheritance), morality, and an individual's relationship with Allah (s.w.t) than it does about commerce.²⁴

With respect to the daily, private lives of all Muslims, Islam has five pillars that are the essential obligations. These are: (1) the profession of faith (the *Shahada* which affirms monotheism in its first part, and the authenticity of Prophet Muhammad (s.a.w) in its second part as it states that "There is no God but Allah; Muhammad is the messenger of Allah"), (2) regular prayer (called *salat* which is performed five times a day), (3) compulsory charity (called *zakat*), (4) fasting during the month of Ramadan (called *sawm*), and (5) pilgrimage (the *Hajj*).²⁵

III. Islamic Finance: Theological and Jurisprudential Underpinnings

Freedom of business in Islam is not absolute as there are some religious strictures. Investments in activities such as gambling or the production of alcohol or pork are forbidden.²⁶ Additionally, to be able to offer financial products under Islamic finance, investments must follow four interrelated rules: 1) avoid interest, called *riba*; 2) avoid excessive risk-taking, called *gharar*; 3) recognize that money is not a commodity; 4) and recognize that money does not have time value, that is to say money does not change in value as time passes.

²⁴ For an interesting discussion of Islamic law see M. Cherif Bassiouni & Gamal M. Badr, *The Shari'ah: Sources, Interpretation, and Rule-Making*, 1 UCLA J. Islamic & Near E. L. 135, 149 (2002) (the Qur'an and the *sunna* contain the greater number of norms applicable to the areas of criminal law, family law, contracts and obligations, procedure, and inheritance law as compared to other subjects within the *mu'amalat* category (societal relations and individual interactions). Being a book [Qur'an] of spiritual guidance and not a legal code, it is not surprising to find only 500 verses with legal content).

²⁵ See Raj Bhala, *Theological Categories for Special and Differential Treatment*, 50 U. Kan. L. Rev. 635, 677 (2002). Muslims, both Sunnis and Shi'ites, are under the ritual obligation to accomplish *hajj* to the holiest sites in Mecca at least once in their lifetime. Shi'ites give importance to visiting the tombs of saints. The great centers of Shi'ite pilgrimage in Iraq are Karbala, Najaf, Samarra, and Kazemeyn. The great center of Shi'ite pilgrimage in Iran is Mashhad. See Richard, *supra* note 21, at 8-9.

²⁶ According to Islamic law, the presumption of general permissibility governs until the contrary is established by an injunctive authority. See Munawar Iqbal & Tariqullah Khan, Introduction, in *Financial Engineering and Islamic Contracts* 1, 2-3 (Munawar Iqbal & Tariqullah Khan eds., 2005).

Riba is translated into English as usury.²⁷ It involves unjust profit or advantage.²⁸ Islamic law and modern business come into conflict when addressing *riba*.²⁹ Islamic theory holds that money should be used in a financial system only to facilitate the purchase or sale of goods and services, but should not for example be “commoditized” by depositing money with banks for a guaranteed return over time. In other words, Islamic law encourages entrepreneurship rather than hoarding of money.

The debate is squared on the issue of whether Islamic law should assign quantity value or time value for money. An example of the quantity value would be when one person lends \$100 in singles to another person for three months. On the one hand, when the money is due, then the second person ought to return the \$100 in singles without regard to its value. On the other hand, according to time value or pure time preference theory, the second person ought to return the \$100 in singles as well as a bit more. Charging a “bit more” could be justified on the basis that if the first person did not lend money he could have invested the money elsewhere in something profitable. Alternatively, during the three month period, the currency may be devalued.

²⁷ The Qur’an states, “Allah has made buying and selling lawful and usury unlawful”. See Qur’an 2: 275-278. From a comparative viewpoint, Judaism and Christianity have prohibited *riba* as well. See Jean-François Seznec, *Ethics, Islamic Banking and the Global Financial Market*, 23-SPG Fletcher World Aff. 161, 165 (1999) (interest and usury are discussed in the Bible in Ezekiel 18:8 and Deuteronomy 23:19. These paragraphs, which apply to Jews and Christians, clearly forbid the use of usury in dealing with people. For centuries, Christians had a very strong prejudice against interest, which they used however reluctantly. The Catholic Church only lifted the ban on interest in the mid-nineteenth century). Today, there are banks in Israel that cater to Jews who refuse to take or pay interest. See Daniel Klein, *The Islamic and Jewish Laws of Usury: A Bridge to Commercial growth and Peace in the Middle East*, 23 Denv. J. Int’l L. & Pol’y 535, 541-544 (1995).

²⁸ *Riba* is of two kinds: *riba al-fadl*, in which a person acquires an unlawful, excessive profit, and *riba al-nasi’a*, in which a person gains an unlawful advantage by speculating on uncontrollable risks. *Riba al-nasi’a* is form of *gharar*.

²⁹ Great amount of literature is devoted to *riba* as to its definition and impact. The core of the debate is what constitutes *riba*. Some classical Muslim jurists define *riba* broadly to include any interest or increase. Other modest jurists define it narrowly to include excessive interest or doubling beyond the real value of money if the borrower defaults during specific time. In the latter view, excessive interest should be prohibited and not any mere increase. Prohibition of *riba* is applied variably in Muslim countries such as Iran, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, and Sudan. For more see Barbara L. Seniawski, *Riba Today: Social Equity, the Economy, and Doing Business under Islamic Law*, 39 Colum. J. Transnatl. L. 701, 707-720 (2001).

Therefore, the value of \$100 three months ago may worth \$50 three months later after indexation.³⁰

Another limitation to business in Islamic law is *gharar* (uncertainty or speculation). An Islamic financial contract is valid if, among other things, there is no ignorance about object, price, time, and the like. Uncertainty generally includes lack of full information, deceit, risk, and inherent uncertainty as to the subject matter of the contract.³¹ *Gharar* involves future contracts in which goods are not determined at the time of contracting. The case of life insurance offers an excellent example of the debate surrounding *gharar*. A person purchases life insurance to secure his family's well-being in case of an unexpected event. In Islamic law, some argue that life insurance is a kind of betting on that person's life.³² Allah (s.w.t) has the control over and knowledge of that person's life.³³ From time immemorial, Allah (s.w.t) pre-determined each person's fate and destiny. On the other hand, other Muslim scholars would argue that modern life in society is complex and unpredictable, which makes life insurance important to individuals. To secure a person's family in case of an unexpected event, alternatives to life insurance there exist in Islamic society such as laws of inheritance, *Zakat*, and social security. Moreover, Islamic

³⁰ The "bit more" presumes devaluation of currency. However, there could be a scenario where the price of the currency increases. As such, the lender would perhaps receive double the amount he gives. In this case, the terms of the agreement between the parties ought to be adjusted to ensure fairness.

³¹ See Mahmoud A. El-Gamal, *Islamic Finance: Law, Economics, and Practice* 59 (2006). See also Haider Ala Hamoudi, *The Muezzin's Call and the Dow Jones Bell: On the Necessity of Realism in the Study of Islamic Law*, 56 *Am. J. Comp. L.* 423, 444 (2008).

³² See Samir Mankabady, *Insurance and Islamic Law: The Islamic Insurance Company*, 4 *Arab L. Q.* 199 (1989) (some Muslim scholars differ on the legality of insurance. *Abu Zhra*, a *Hanafi* scholar, believed that cooperative insurance is legal. Other types of insurance could not be placed under the groups of contracts known in Islamic law: sale, donation, and hire). See Mohd. Masum Billah, *Life Insurance? An Islamic View*, 8 *Arab L. Q.* 315-319 (1993) (other grounds against the validity of life insurance include *riba* since the beneficiaries of the assured will gain more than the assured has paid to the insurer. This additional gain is *riba*). See also Ahmad A. Al-Ghadyan, *Insurance: The Islamic Perspective and its Development in Saudi Arabia*, *Arab L. Q.* 332-335 (1999).

³³ See Qur'an 31:34.

insurance, known in Arabic as *takaful*, as opposed to conventional insurance, can operate in line with Islamic concepts.³⁴

Islamic law prohibits the sale of commodities before they are delivered to the buyer such as the sale of fish in the sea, unripe fruit on a tree, or the fetus of a camel.³⁵ Accordingly, conventional instruments such as options, futures and forward contracts may not be available in Islamic financial institutions.³⁶ The requirement of a physical, legitimate and productive asset in a financial transaction presents a strong of Islamic finance. This requirement prevents the illusion of profitability, which may be wiped out by currency fluctuations or the decline in value of options or futures. Islamic instruments, based on the securitization of productive legitimate assets, offer a great avenue for investment and perhaps are the greatest strength in the growth of Islamic finance. At any rate, if the theory of *gharar* were applied narrowly, it would make economic life impossible.³⁷ After all, there is an element of speculation and uncertainty in everything. It would be appropriate to develop a benchmark against which “excessive” speculation is considered *gharar*.

³⁴ Islamic insurance functions like conventional cooperative insurance. In cooperative insurance, resources in insurance companies are pooled whereby policyholders are considered shareholders sharing in profits. However, in a *takaful* company, policyholders and shareholders are distinct in which both own capital and share in annual profits. *Retakaful* insurance also functions like conventional reinsurance.

³⁵ See Frank E. Vogel & Samuel L. Hayes, III, *Islamic Law and Finance: Religion, Risk and Return* 87-88 (1998).

³⁶ See Nazih Hammad, *Compensation for an Obligation to Sell Currency in the Future (Hedging)*, 7 *Chi. J. Int'l L.* 521, 528 (2007) (analyzing whether Islamic law permits forward currency contracts. The lawfulness of forward currency contracts depends on the purpose of buying the obligation. If the purpose of buying the obligation is no more than to speculate on currency prices-with the expectation of benefiting from a rise in prices-rather than to actually take possession of the currency, then the usufruct sought from the purchase will not be a lawful one. This is because such a purpose resembles gambling).

³⁷ For more on this matter see Sajjad M. Jasimuddin, *The Stock Exchange and Islamic Finance: Some Thoughts for a Reconsideration*, Vol. 14 *The Islamic Q.* 105, 108 (No. 2, 2001) (some Islamic scholars found stock exchange objectionable because Islamic law does not permit the sale of an article until one has the physical possession of it. Trading in stocks is usually done without their physical possession and there is an element of chance. Therefore, trading in shares, bonds, and debentures is objectionable. Stock exchange is further objectionable for its elements of speculation. On the other hand, other Islamic scholars argue that speculation in the stock exchange is a process that involves the intelligent forecasting of future prices. This is not the same as tossing dice).

A. Conventional Finance vs. Islamic Finance

The nature and concept of Islamic finance is the sharing of profit and loss by lenders and borrowers. Under Islamic finance, the lender or investor cannot receive a monetary benefit if there is no sharing of risk on his part. In determining risk, Islamic finance is concerned primarily with the viability and profitability of operations, not the size of collateral, as is the case in conventional financing.

Islamic finance uses a different approach than conventional finance. For instance, under conventional finance, XYZ wants to buy a vehicle for US \$20,000 and so requests a loan from the bank for that amount. The bank agrees by giving a twelve month loan provided that XYZ pays say US \$100 per month in addition to the principal amount of say US \$1000 a month. In summation, the bank charges US \$100 a month for providing the US \$20,000 loan. In other words, the bank charges money for extending the loan, i.e. interest.³⁸ The interest will continue to accumulate until the principal amount and interest are paid.

By contrast, under Islamic mode of finance, the bank first makes XYZ its agent. Thus, XYZ buys the vehicle on behalf of the bank, the principal party, for US \$20,000. The bank then sells the vehicle to XYZ for the price of US \$20,600. Although the end result of Islamic finance seems similar to convention finance, the approach is completely different.³⁹ Under Islamic finance, the bank initially buys the asset and then sells the asset to the client for a profit.⁴⁰ In case of default, the total amount of US \$20,600 does not change because it is considered a sale contract whereby

³⁸ This is a lending contract.

³⁹ Critics may argue that "profit" in Islamic finance is just another name for interest and that Islamic financial institutions use the same rates as conventional financial institutions use to determine their profits. See Mahmoud A. El-Gamal, *"Interest" and the Paradox of Contemporary Islamic Law and Finance*, 27 Fordham Intl L J 108, 108-09 (2004). See also Kelly Holden, *Islamic Finance: "Legal Hypocrisy" Moot Point, Problematic Future Bigger Concern*, 25 B.U. Int'l L.J. 341, 349 (2007) (the more traditional Islamic scholars argue that Islamic financial instruments are too similar to conventional banking - the legal hypocrisy).

⁴⁰ This is a sale contract.

the sale price of the asset is fixed at the time of contracting. Hence, if the client defaults, he pays US \$20,600 only.

B. Instruments of Islamic Finance

To avoid the issues of *riba* and *gharar*, new alternatives have been developed to make business possible and finance trade. These alternatives are *mudaraba*, *musharaka*, and *murabaha*. All these alternatives include the concept of sharing profit and loss.⁴¹

1. Mudaraba (Trust Finance)⁴²

Mudaraba is a business undertaking in which a person participates with his money and another with his effort and skill.⁴³ The owner of the capital is known as *rab'ilmal* and the other partner is known as *mudarib*. In other words, it is a contract in which an investor entrusts his money to another party called an entrepreneur for making profit.⁴⁴ Therefore, it is a form of a business association like a partnership. The *mudarib* will have the money at his disposal for investment in transactions he considers most appropriate. Profits from the investment are shared between *rab'ilmal* and *mudarib* at a predetermined ratio. Any accrued losses are borne by the *rab'ilmal*.

Financial institutions provide *mudaraba* banking by reformulating deposit money as partnership capital. The bank monitors the investment and can act as the sole partner. The monitoring costs of *mudaraba* are, as one would anticipate, significantly higher than in Western

⁴¹ Islamic finance is based on the concept of profit and loss sharing with Islamic banks being willing to take on risks associated with title and to participate in the financial structures established for their clients. It is not based on the concept of guaranteed return without any notion of risk or participation. Muhammad Ayub, *Understanding Islamic Finance* 44-57 (John Wiley & Sons 2007).

⁴² *Mudaraba* is also known as *Qirad* and *Muqaraba*.

⁴³ *Mudaraba* is a pre-Islamic custom used to finance the caravan trade in Arabia. It is an example of a commercial arrangement identical to the economic and legal institution which became known in Europe as the *Commenda*. *Id.* 320.

⁴⁴ The investor will have his capital and a predetermined profit between himself and the entrepreneur. The profits, if any, are shared upon in advance, but not as a guaranteed return. Thus, the profits are uncertain in this case. The loss, if any, is borne only by the investor and must not exceed the amount of capital, unless the loss is due to negligence by the *mudarib*. If the loss is equivalent to the capital, the Islamic bank will receive nothing. *Id.* 323-327.

banking because active oversight of businesses is required. The potential return on capital in these relationships is also much greater. Large Islamic banks, which are usually involved in numerous equity partnerships, tend to pool their *mudaraba* investments, returning a percentage proportional to the depositor's capital.

The structure of the *mudaraba* contract provides an opportunity to participate in large projects, sharing in risks and profits. *Mudaraba* is a vehicle for banks to raise funding for projects that are considered too large or risky.⁴⁵ Investment funds, based on the *mudaraba* principle, allow investors to invest in trade finance deals, commodities trade, and market securities. These investment funds are flexible as the individual investor is free to choose the type of investment he favors. Also, these investment funds provide assurance to the Muslim investor that the portfolio components are in compliance with *shari'a* principals.

2. *Musharaka* (Partnership Finance)

Musharaka can be defined as a partnership between two or more persons. *Musharaka* can be divided into two forms: contractual partnership and non-contractual partnership. On the one hand, non-contractual partnership comes into existence when two or more persons get joint ownership of some asset without entering into a formal relationship. For example, non-contractual partnership exists when two persons receive an inheritance. On the other, in a contractual partnership parties enter willingly into a partnership.

⁴⁵ Islamic banks undertake *mudaraba* from their asset and liability sides. As for the asset side, Islamic banks become the capital owner and use their deposit funds as the capital. Islamic banks are generally authorized by the deposit holders to pool their funds toward capital investment by the Islamic bank. As for the liability side, Islamic banks become the investment manager, with depositors serving as capital owners. The depositors authorize the Islamic bank to mix their capital with its own funds - absence of this authorization will invalidate the pooling of funds. Profits are distributed according to an agreed proportion, but losses must be borne in proportion to the capital provided by each party. See Philip Molyneux & Munawar Iqbal, *Banking and Financial System in the Arab World* 169 (2005).

Contractual partnership includes four kinds.⁴⁶ First, a contractual partnership could be a partnership whereby two persons pool their physical and/or mental labor without sharing capital investment. Any profits will be shared according to their agreement.⁴⁷ Second, contractual partnership could also involve partners who use their reputation and goodwill rather than capital. The third kind of contractual partnership enjoys equality in the areas of capital, management, and right of settlement. All profits and losses are shared equally among the partners. The fourth kind of contractual partnership involves partners that need not be equals in their contribution of capital or management.⁴⁸ However, an additional share of the profit will be granted to the partner who manages the enterprise. In this kind of partnership, there is no set formula for profit sharing and each case is dealt with on its own merit. The amount of liability is limited to the percentage of his share in the enterprise.

The difference between *musharaka* and *mudaraba* is that in most cases of *musharaka*, all involved parties provide capital to share in the profit or loss of the project. In *mudaraba*, one party provides the capital and the other acts as an agent to invest it. The agent in a *mudaraba* does not share in the losses. *Musharaka* is essentially unsecured funding and exposes banks to a higher risk. However, the risk in the *musharaka* can be mitigated by choosing an appropriate security structure.

3. *Murabaha* (Cost-Plus Financing)

Murabaha can be defined as the purchase price of goods plus a fixed profit. It is a kind of sale contract in which the final price includes the cost plus profit, which is known to the parties in advance without any deception. An example of this type of Islamic finance is a form of auto

⁴⁶ See Umar F. Moghul, *No Pain, No Gain: The State of the Industry in Light of an American Islamic Private Equity Transaction*, 7 Chi. J. Int'l L. 469, 481-482 (2007).

⁴⁷ *Id.*

⁴⁸ *Id.*

finance. If a person wants to buy a vehicle, he can request an Islamic bank to purchase it from a dealer and resell it to him at the original purchase price plus a negotiated profit on agreed terms. The negotiated profit, or mark-up, would compensate the bank for its time and effort spent for communication, currency exchange, etc. *Murabaha* could be used as a long-term financing instrument.⁴⁹ Nevertheless, *murabaha* usually serves as a short-term funding instrument, i.e., one or two years.

Murabaha has its own risks. For example, *murabaha* finance requires banks to deal in commodities which many lending institutions hesitate to deal with.⁵⁰ Moreover, as real intermediaries, banks face difficulties such as assumption of risk, guarantees, insurance, default, and maintenance.

Murabaha is the main product of Islamic finance compared with *mudaraba* and *musharaka* instruments.⁵¹ *Murabaha* can be differentiated from *mudaraba* in that in *murabaha*, an Islamic financial institution is no longer to share profits or losses, but instead assume the capacity of a traditional financial intermediary. Additionally, *murabaha* can be distinguished from conventional lending whereby a bank is concerned with the creditworthiness of a borrower. In

⁴⁹ For example, *murabaha* structure was implemented for a power plant expansion, and related transmission facilities for a Saudi Arabian electric utility company in 1998. The Utility Power Project transaction involved five parties: the Utility, three banks providing financing, and an engineering, procurement, and construction contractor. The tenor of the financing was seven years, involving a two-year construction period and a five-year financing repayment period. The *murabaha* portion of the financing structure involved the sale of parts by banks to the Utility from time to time. Michael J.T. McMillen, *Islamic Shari'ah-Compliant Project Finance: Collateral Security and Financing Structure Case Studies*, 24 *Fordham Int'l L.J.* 1184, 1234-1236 (2001). See also Umar F. Moghul and Arshad A. Ahmed, *Contractual Forms in Islamic Finance Law and Islamic Inv. Co. of the Gulf (Bahama) Ltd. V. Symphony Gems N.V. & ORS.: A First Impression of Islamic Finance*, 27 *Fordham Int'l L.J.* 150, 185 (2003) (In January 2000, the claimant Islamic Investment Company of the Gulf (Bahamas) Ltd. (IICG) entered into a *murabaha* financing agreement with the defendant Symphony Gems N.V. (Symphony). The Contract envisaged that IICG would provide a revolving purchase and sale facility to enable Symphony to purchase certain inventory, namely precious stones and gems. The Contract, according to the terms contained in its recitals, intended for the financing to follow the form of a *murabahah* transaction and, thereby, to be in compliance with the Shari'ah).

⁵⁰ The reason for this hesitation is that a bank could end up with the commodity if the person defaults on payment or refuses to accept the commodity. The Islamic bank, as a title holder, will bear any risk to the goods during the time of its ownership up to the time the person examines and accepts them.

⁵¹ *Murabaha* accounts for about seventy-five percent of Islamic finance transactions. See Calling the faithful; Islamic Finance, *The Economist* (Dec. 9, 2006). See also Tom Wright and Yayu Yuniar, Islamic Finance Widens Pitch --- Banks Aim to Show Shariah Products Can Be Competitive, *WALL ST. J.*, Sep. 5, 2007, at B3.

contrast, in *murabaha* type of lending, an Islamic bank would be concerned with more than creditworthiness. An Islamic bank would be concerned with profitability since it would enter into profit/loss sharing arrangement. An Islamic bank would be careful to double-check the profitability of an enterprise before putting its capital in. Therefore, it would be difficult for an Islamic bank to check bookkeeping of an enterprise or for an entrepreneur to declare himself as less profitable which might be true as a matter of fact. In *murabaha* if the client defaults, the selling price of the contract cannot be changed.⁵² The client is only liable to pay the agreed sale price of the asset. In conventional finance, on the other hand, if the client defaults he remains responsible for interest payments due on the principal and interest until the loan is paid off.

4. *Ijara* (Lease Financing)

Ijara can be used to provide funding for plant and machinery purchases.⁵³ Under this type of financing, the bank agrees to purchase the equipment and lease it to the client for a rental fee. Details such as the duration of the lease and the amount of rent are determined in the contract. The bank, as lessor, has ownership of the equipment. However, *Ijara* can provide an option, known as *ijara wa-iqtina*, which allows the lessee to purchase the equipment at the end of the lease term.⁵⁴ The price of the equipment in the latter case is essentially the rent and is paid to the lessor over the agreed period of time.

⁵² See Sina Ali Muscati, *Late Payment in Islamic Finance*, 6 UCLA J. Islamic & Near E.L. 47, 54 (2006) (Muslim bankers should instead accept the problem of default or late payment with understanding, patience and a hope of being rewarded in the Hereafter, and rely on other measures to deter late payment. Such measures could include improved background checks to screen clients, or requiring that clients furnish security to secure payment on the due date).

⁵³ See Angelo Luigi Rosa, *Harmonizing Risk and Religion: The Utility of Shari'a-Compliant Transaction Structuring in Commercial Aircraft Finance*, 13 Minn. J. Global Trade 35, 45 (2003) (In the context of the aircraft finance transaction, the most applicable concepts in the Islamic finance milieu are *ijara* methods of finance).

⁵⁴*Id.*

There are differences between *ijara* and a conventional lease. In *ijara*, the lease begins the day the asset is delivered to the client while in conventional lease the lease begins on the day the contract is signed. The lessee is not liable for the full amount of rent if the asset is destroyed.⁵⁵ Further, as part of the *ijara*, the purchase of the asset at the end of the lease contract cannot be made mandatory. Thus, the lessee cannot be punished for not purchasing the asset.

5. *Istisna* (Commissioned Manufacturing)

Istisna is mainly used for assets which are manufactured. A bank finances the construction of permissible assets that can be precisely determined by description and specifications.⁵⁶ Although the liability to pay for the construction, and deliver the constructed assets, will be that of the bank providing the financing, the bank does not have to itself construct the assets. The financing bank (*sane'*) may contract with a third party (*mustasne*) to construct the assets so long as this arrangement entails no contractual obligations between the bank client that ultimately desires to purchase the constructed assets and the construction contractor. The bank client is permitted to inspect and supervise the construction activities to insure compliance with the specifications and

⁵⁵ Generally, a financial institution takes out insurance on the asset and factors in the cost of insurance at the time the rent is fixed.

⁵⁶ An Islamic construction financing structure was implemented in a U.S. residential housing transaction in Austin, Texas (Maconda Park Project). In April 2001, that construction financing structure was implemented in a second U.S. residential housing transaction in Largo, Maryland (Truman Park Project). In connection with the development of each of the Projects, the Developers, in each case through Key Global Capital, arranged both equity investments and Islamic debt-equivalent financing. The Islamic equity financing was provided primarily by Gulf Investment House of Kuwait in each transaction. In the Maconda Park transaction, the Developer and the Islamic Investors formed the Maconda Project Company, with each such entity making equity contributions. The Maconda Project Company, using such equity contributions and the other financing amounts provided by KeyBank through the related Owner as described herein, purchased, and holds title to, the Maconda Site and the other portions of the Maconda Premises. The Maconda Project Company leased the Maconda Site and granted other rights to the remainder of the Maconda Premises to the Owner pursuant to a Site Lease. In the Truman Park transaction, the Developer had previously formed the Truman Project Company and had purchased the Truman Site prior to the conversion of the conventional construction loan to an *istisna'a-ijara* financing structure. The Islamic Investors made equity contributions to the Truman Project Company after restructuring of that company. The Truman Project Company, using such equity contributions and the other financing amounts provided by KeyBank through the Owner as described herein, converted the conventional loan financing to an Islamic financing and undertook construction of the Truman Park Project. The Truman Project Company leased the Truman Site and granted other rights to the remainder of the Truman Premises to the related Owner pursuant to a Site Lease. See McMillen, *supra* note 49, at 1237-1247.

for other purposes. The bank client may accept delivery of the constructed assets on behalf of the bank.

Under *istisna*, the payment may be paid in advance (*ba'i al-salam*) or on a deferred basis (*ba'i bithaman ajil*).⁵⁷ Under *ba'i bithaman ajil*, initially the bank purchases the contract to buy the assets, equipment or goods as requested by the client and subsequently sells them to the client at an agreed-upon price.⁵⁸ The bank's selling price includes its profit margin. The bank makes progressive payments to the supplier as the asset is purchased or manufactured. The client can repay in lump sum or make installment payments over an agreed-upon period. *Ba'i bithaman ajil* is similar to a *murabaha* contract as it also is a credit sale.

⁵⁷ See Christopher F. Richardson, *Islamic Finance Opportunities in the Oil and Gas Sector: An Introduction to an Emerging Field*, 42 Tex. Int'l L.J. 119, 127 (2006).

⁵⁸ See J. Michael Taylor, *Islamic Banking: The Feasibility of Establishing an Islamic Bank in the United States*, 40 Am. Bus. L.J. 385, 396 (2003).

Conclusion

Not only does Islam cover morality and individual's relationship with Allah (s.w.t), but also does cover business transactions. Islam regulates every aspect of life. The fact that the Prophet Muhammad (s.a.w) started his career as a merchant is unique to the Islamic Prophecy. The Shari'ah blends holy scripture and oral traditions with multiple styles of human interpretation. Shari'ah is a living law.

Although Islamic law is inclined toward business and free trade, there are certain limitations. These limitations include the prohibition of trade in illegitimate goods such as pork and alcohol. In other words, goods that are in conformity with Islamic teachings are acceptable. Otherwise, these goods and services are prohibited. The other limitations to business in Islam are *riba* and *gharar*. To avoid these latter limitations and finance trade, new alternatives have been developed.

Islamic finance stands at the intersections of law, economics, and religion. The Islamic financial markets currently provide an array of financial instruments such as *mudaraba*, *musharaka*, and *murabaha*. These instruments are based upon the concept of sharing profit and loss. Islamic finance is based on the trade of productive assets, the sharing of risks in the development of projects, the promotion of entrepreneurship and the provision of social benefits to those who are often exploited by lenders.

Islamic finance has just begun to grapple with the application of Islamic law to modern circumstances and how to address present-day commercial practices from an Islamic point of view. The continuing growth of Islamic finance as an alternative to conventional finance breeds competition that will benefit borrowers. On account of this competition, there is an unprecedented pressure for innovation. Moreover, Islamic finance offers an additional avenue for raising funds from Muslim investors by allowing consumers and financiers to choose financial instruments that are compatible with their business needs, social values and religious beliefs.

Business and trade in Islam are used with an Islamic “purifier”. In a nutshell, Islamic law embraces Islamic market economy.